

Variation of Mobility Ratios of Cations through Membranes with Concentration and Simultaneous Determination of Activities of Ions in Binary Mixtures

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The mobility ratio U_{ca}/U_{Na} of clay and resin membranes have been determined using in both cases the same activity ratios. Dependence of U_{ca}/U_{Na} on ionic proportions has been examined. Bionic activities in mixture have been measured using membrane electrodes having different mobility ratios.

Wyllie¹ derived equations for the potentials which are set up when perfectly selective ion-exchange membranes separate mixtures of critical ions. When ions separated are of like valency the equations are relatively simple but complex when valencies of ions are dissimilar. The membrane potential, E_M for the case

is given by

$$E_M = \frac{RT}{F} \left[\frac{a_{Na}^{II} - a_{Na}^I + \frac{U_{ca}}{U_{Na}} a_{Ca}^{II}}{a_{Na}^{II} - a_{Na}^I + 2 \frac{U_{ca}}{U_{Na}} a_{Ca}^{II}} \right] \ln \frac{a_{Na}^I}{a_{Na}^{II} + 2 \frac{U_{ca}}{U_{Na}} a_{Ca}^{II}} \quad (1)$$

where the terms have their usual significance. U_{ca}/U_{Na} , the mobility ratio is dependent on the cationic activities and also on the nature of the membranes.

McLean, Barber, and Marshall² found even in the case of ions of the same valency, some variation of mobility ratio with ionic activities. Their data also suggested dependence of mobility on cationic proportions.

Bose³ observed dependence of mobility ratio on activity but the variation was not regular.

The evaluation of U_{ca}/U_{Na} is very tedious owing to the awkward form of the equation and hence some approximations are necessary. Three special cases may be considered.

1. M. R. J. Wyllie, *J. Physical Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 67.
2. E. O. McLean, S. A. Barber and C. E. Marshall, *Soil Science*, 1951, **72**, No. 4,
3. S. K. Bose, *Jour. Indian Soc., Soil Sci.*, 1955, **3**, No. 1.

Case-I, $a^I_{Na} > a^{II}_{ca}, a^{II}_{Na} = 0$

$$E_M = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a^I_{Na}}{2 \frac{U_{ca}}{U_{Na}} a^{II}_{ca}} \quad \dots (2)$$

Case-II, $a^I_{Na} = a^{II}_{Na}$

$$E_M = \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{a^I_{Na}}{a^{II}_{Na} + 2 \frac{U_{ca}}{U_{Na}} a^{II}_{ca}} \quad \dots (3)$$

Case-III, $a^I_{Na} > \left[a^{II}_{Na} + \frac{U_{ca}}{U_{Na}} \cdot a^{II}_{ca} \right]$

$$E_M = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a^I_{Na}}{a^{II}_{Na} + 2 \frac{U_{ca}}{U_{Na}} a^{II}_{ca}} \quad \dots (4)$$

If standard solutions of known activities are placed on the two sides of a membrane, then a determination of E_M enables calculations of appropriate mobility ratio from the equations referred to above.

In the absence of suitably selective electrodes, activities of two cations when present in a mixture can be evaluated if two equations are set up for the same mixture. This can be done by selecting two membranes which have as wide values of mobility ratios as possible⁴.

In this connection the remark of McLean *et al.*² regarding the accuracy of the determination of mobility ratio in mixture is to be kept in mind.

The present paper reports U_{ca}/U_{Na} values of a clay and a resin membrane electrode and their dependence on cationic proportions.

Ion activities in mixtures have been determined by using two membranes having different U_{ca}/U_{Na} .

EXPERIMENTAL

The clay membrane electrodes were prepared from *Ca*-saturated montmorillonitic Chinsurah clay by heating thin films at 600° obtained in the usual way for 48 hr. The resin membrane is a product of Ionac Co. obtained through the courtesy of Dr. C. Calman of Ionic Chemical Company, Birmingham, N.J. The membranes were fixed with polystyrene based adhesive at the flat end of pyrex tubes and were tested by the usual procedure for their performance for Na^+ and Ca^{+2} ion activity measurements. Saturated calomel electrodes having less than 0.2 mv. asymmetry potential were used as reference electrodes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table I (case I) illustrates the variation of U_{ca}/U_{Na} with concentration for the same *Ca/Na* activity ratio. In the case of clay membrane electrodes, it decreases slightly as activity decreases.

TABLE I

$$a_{\text{Na}^+}/a_{\text{Ca}^{+2}} = 9.74$$

Inner Soln. (a_{Na^+})	Outr Soln. ($a_{\text{Ca}^{+2}}$)	EMF(mv)	$U_{\text{Ca}}/U_{\text{Na}}$
0.0789	0.0081	A. 15.2	2.7
		B. 3.0	4.3
0.0263	0.0027	A. 9.5	3.5
		B. 10.9	3.2
0.0087	0.0009	A. 23.0	2.0
		B. 33.0	1.3
0.00292	0.0003	A. 21.6	2.1
		B. 22.4	2.0
0.0097	0.0001	A. 20.6	2.2
		B. 35.3	1.2

In the case of resin membrane electrode, however, the variation of $U_{\text{Ca}}/U_{\text{Na}}$ is more marked.

In Table II (case II) $U_{\text{Ca}}/U_{\text{Na}}$ varies regularly from 0.45 to 11.

TABLE II

			$(a_{\text{Na}^+}^{\text{I}})$	$(a_{\text{Na}^+}^{\text{II}})$	$(a_{\text{Ca}^{+2}}^{\text{II}})$	
0.0789	0.0789	0.0027	A. 7			4.5
			B. 6			3.8
0.0263	0.0263	0.0027	A. 4.9			1.0
			B. 5.8			1.2
0.0087	0.0087	0.0081	A. 15.4			0.45
			B. 21.0			0.70
0.00292	0.00292	0.0003	A. 20.2			10.7
			B. 21.2			11.1
0.0097	0.0097	0.0009	A. 20			2.0
			B. 19			1.8

A = Clay membrane (600°C)

B = Resin membrane.

Table III (case III) shows that $U_{\text{Ca}}/U_{\text{Na}}$ increases with $a_{\text{Na}^+}^{\text{II}}$ with both clay and resin membrane electrodes where $a_{\text{Na}^+}^{\text{I}}$ and $a_{\text{Ca}^{+2}}^{\text{II}}$ are constant but $a_{\text{Na}^+}^{\text{II}}$ increases.

TABLE III

0.0789	0.0	0.0003	A. 110.0	1.9
			B. 80.0	6.1
	0.0097		A. 92.4	2.0
			B. 71.0	7.0
	0.00292		A. 76.0	2.2
			B. 62.2	7.2
	0.0087		A. 51.0	3.9
			B. 45.0	8.8

Table IV illustrates the variation of U_{ca}/U_{Na} when a_{Na}^I and a_{Na}^{II} are constant but a_{ca}^{II} changes. Here U_{ca}/U_{Na} decreases with a_{ca}^{II} similar to the case mentioned above.

TABLE IV

Inner Soln (a_{Na}^I)	Outer Soln (a_{Na}^{II})		EMF(mv.)	U_{ca}/U_{Na}
	(a_{Na}^I)	(a_{ca}^{II+2})		
0.0789	0.0087	0.0001	A. 52.5	8.7
			B. 47.0	21.0
		0.003	A. 51.0	3.9
			B. 45.0	8.8
		0.0009	A. 43.2	3.5
			B. 30.0	9.0
0.0263	0.0087	0.001	A. 26.0	4.6
			B. 24.2	7.3
		0.0009	A. 17.2	2.8
			B. 13.3	3.8
		0.0081	A. -3.9	1.3
			B. -8.7	1.7
0.0087	0.00292	0.0001	A. 24.0	2.9
			B. 22.1	4.2
		0.0003	A. 16.1	3.0
			B. 20.5	1.8
0.0097	0.0097	0.0001	A. 20.6	2.2
			B. 35.3	1.25
		0.0003	A. 8.1	1.9
			B. 6.5	1.94
		0.0009	A. 20.0	1.98
			B. 19.0	1.8

Mclean *et al.*² observed the dependence of mobility ratios on cationic proportion in contact with the membrane surface and our data paper confirm their observations. It is due to the fact that critical ions are constrained in their mobilities during their transference through membrane and this stems from the attraction for critical ions in the exchange sites of the pore of ion exchange membrane. According to Bose³ it is due to the difference in the speed of the ions inside the membrane. This attraction for critical ions in the exchange sites or difference in the speed inside the membrane is probably dependent on cationic proportion. The variation of U_{ca}/U_{Na} is also dependent on the nature of the exchange surface. It is more marked in the resin membrane whereas in the case of clay membrane the variation of U_{ca}/U_{Na} is not so pronounced.

Since a constant value of U_{ca}/U_{Na} is not obtained, a difficulty will arise in the determination of unknown activities with the help of membrane electrodes. If approximate activities are known, then corresponding mobility ratio may be used for the calculation of unknown ion activities.

Table V illustrates the determination of unknown activities using the appropriate values of mobility ratios of clay and a resin membrane electrode for the relevant cation pair.

TABLE V

Mixture contents	Actual Activities	Inner Reference Soln.	Observed Activities	U_{Ca}/U_{Na}
Na ⁺ , Ca ⁺²	$a_{Na^+} : 0.0263$	$a_{Na^+} : 0.0263$	0.027	A. 2.8
	$a_{Ca^{+2}} : 0.0081$		0.0079	B. 3.8

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